

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D1.2 Quality Assurance Plan, and guidelines for consortium operation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the strategy to implement an appropriate coordination framework. It presents guidelines, key issues, and achievements. It includes project organisation, communication among partners, reporting tools, organisation of deliverables, financial management, and quality procedures.

The main points included in this deliverable are:

- Description of the project structure, including roles and responsibilities.
- Documents of reference.
- Overall project status and progress monitoring of the work.
- Project reporting procedures including financial reporting.
- Disseminations of the project.
- Assessment of risk management.

This deliverable is a guideline for the partners to have a common understanding of project procedures to efficiently implement it and achieve the objectives fixed in the Grant Agreement. Its purpose is to complement the information already provided by the Grant agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
T	Task
TOC	Table of Content
WP	Work-Package
WPL	Work-Package Leader
PC	Project Coordinator
PU	Public
SEN	Sensitive
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
PI	Principal Investigator
LEAR	Legal Entity Appointed Representative
i2CAT	FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA
URV	UNIVERSITAT ROVIRA I VIRGILI
FURV	FUNDACIO URV
F6S	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED
HAM	BEHOERDE FUER ARBEIT, GESUNDHEIT, SOZIALES, FAMILIE UND INTEGRATION HAMBURG
UJ	UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI
KTP	KRAKOWSKI PARK TECHNOLOGICZNY SP ZOO
SHINE	SHINE 2EUROPE LDA
AFE	AFEDEMY, ACADEMY ON AGE-FRIENDLY ENVIRONMENTS IN EUROPE BV

1. Project structure and reference documents.

1.1 Overview

The main purpose of the INTEGER project management structure is to establish an appropriate framework to achieve the effective implementation of the project. This structure will allow effective day-by-day management, faster decision-making processes and the better implementation of the work plan.

In short, the **General Assembly** is the decision-making body of the consortium. The **Project Coordinator (PC)** shall be the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in this Consortium Agreement.

1.2 Reference Documents

There are two documents that define the rights and obligations that apply to the entities involved in the project, the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. The first regulates the contractual obligations with the EC and the Consortium Agreement is the internal agreement between the consortium members.

Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement (GA) is the contract signed between beneficiaries and the Commission. The signature of this contract will determine beneficiaries' commitments. It has seven parts:

- Terms and Conditions
- Annex 1 Description of the action (DoA)
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action
- Annex 3 Accession Forms
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements
- Annex 5 Specific rules

Any modification of the Grant Agreement must be approved by the General Assembly, the EC and implemented through an amendment of the document. The latest version of the document will be uploaded in the Participant Portal and in consortium management space within theglocal.network project platform.

Consortium Agreement

The CA regulates the relationship among the Parties, in particular concerning the organisation of the work between the Parties, the management of the project and the rights and obligations of the parties concerning inter alia liability, access rights and dispute resolution. In our case, the CA is based on an adaptation of the DESCA model.

Just as the Grant Agreement, any modification of the Consortium Agreement must be approved by the General Assembly and implemented through an amendment of the document. The latest version of the document can be found on the intranet.

1.3 Organisation and Roles

The roles of the Partners, as well as the consortium government structures, are defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). Below the main bodies and their responsibilities and roles are presented.

General Assembly	Highest body of the INTEGER project and ultimate decision-making body.
Chaired by	Project coordinator: Antonia Caro (i2CAT)
Participants	All partners, one member per partner.
Attributions	<p>The General Assembly will assume responsibility for deciding the technical, political and strategic orientation of the project. The General Assembly should approve any modification of GA or CA and any evolution of the consortium. Mainly, the General Assembly will also follow these aspects: (1) Control the execution of the project. (2) Budget follow-up and payments. (3) Manage the changes in the CA and GA. (4) Conflict resolution.</p> <p>The General Assembly will be convened by the Chair along one of the consortium monthly meetings. It can also be convened for extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any Member.</p>

Project Coordinator	Coordinates the activities of all partners in the project according to work plan, and provides the Commission with technical, managerial and financial information.
Contact	Antonia Caro (i2CAT)
Attributions	<p>The PC coordinates the activities of all partners in the project according to the work plan and will act as the unique focal point for contacts and coordination with the European Commission (EC), with other relevant projects, and external relationships with relevant bodies and other related activities. The Project Coordinator chairs the General Assembly. The PC will be in charge of supervision of the overall project progress, the distribution of EC's payments to partners and the Consortium Agreement coordination. The PC will prepare the reports, coordinate the technical work and the technical issues of EC reviews, in addition to monitor the alignment of the project work with the project technical objectives. The PC will be a solution provider of all technical conflicts among tasks and coordinate the internal review of EC deliverables, the dissemination and communication activities.</p>

	Besides that, the PC will organise the EC review meetings, supervise the IPR and knowledge management.
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1. Overall project status and progress monitoring of the work

2.1 Project collaborative platform and email communication

The development of the project, as well as the main communications about it, take place through the platform theglobal.network. This is a place where consortium partners and key regional and international stakeholders meet and exchange in English and in their own languages on questions, needs, demands and provisions at local or regional, interregional or EU levels.

Image 1-Intranet landing page.

This platform is based on **co-creation**, involving different stakeholders collaborating with other participants in order to create and improve new products and services. Co-creation enables the whole group to also participate in the design process, beyond just listening to their ideas, thus empowering them to take part and work together. Becoming a member of theglobal.network benefits to an early access to contact details of local/regional partners, local/regional funding programmes, inspirational cases, activities, innovations, developments and networking opportunities.

Moreover, the Platform is organised by **Channels**, where stakeholders can co-create with other members of the channel. Here interesting content for the Community can be published, look for new partners or co-create with them.

Image 2-Intranet channels.

2.2 Meetings

Meetings can be either face to face, virtual or hybrid meetings. For each meeting the following documentation will be produced and uploaded on the intranet:

- **Notifications:** All formal face to face meetings will be notified at least three weeks in advance. Virtual meetings will be notified as soon as possible.
- **Documentation:** Agenda and supporting documentation will be available to all attendees at least one week before the face to face meeting. In virtual meetings, agenda and discussions points will be shared as soon as possible through intranet or email.
- **Minutes:** Meeting minutes of all meetings (F2F or online) will be formally reported. The chairperson shall produce written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending or uploading, no member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes. Face to face minutes will have to include a list of participants on each day of the meeting. Virtual meetings minutes will have to include a list of the participants attending the call.

2.3 Hosting a face to face meeting

Throughout the project lifetime, members may host project meetings.

- With the aim of avoiding extra costs, it is advisable that the location is reachable for all partners. The host has to provide logistic information on how to reach the venue of the meeting.
- The costs of hosting the meeting will be covered by the hosting partner and the travel costs will be covered by each participant.

- The host must provide meeting rooms with audio-visual equipment necessary for the presentations and network connectivity.

It is also recommended (general practice although not obligatory) to provide water, coffee breaks and lunch and to organise one social event (e.g., invite partners for one evening meal).

2.4 General Assembly voting rules

The General Assembly is the ultimate decision-making body. Decisions will be made by consensus whenever possible. Only in case of conflict, a decision will be made by voting, where each partner will have a power of one vote.

- Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast.
- A Party which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, IPR or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of the General Assembly may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.
- Quorum: each consortium member shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented.

2. Project Reporting

3.1 General rules

The following general rules will be followed for all the outputs of the project:

- **Language:** English is the official language. In consequence all relevant documents and written communications will be written in English. The only exception is related to the dissemination materials, such as press releases or technical publications, which can be translated to other languages. In this scenario, each partner is responsible for translation of official documents to its language of interest.
- **Responsibility:** Each partner is responsible for the quality of their contribution and should provide the information to fulfil any requirement to complete a deliverable, milestone or report. The editor of the document is responsible for the overall quality of the work, including requesting and collecting contributions and integrating them in the different releases.
- The PC will provide templates to ensure a homogenous output of all project documents. It is mandatory for all partners to follow the project templates. When needed each template will provide a style guide for assuring a coherent output.

3.2 Events that must be immediately reported

The partners must inform immediately the PC, who will inform the Project Officer through the PC and the Consortium, of any events which are likely to affect significantly or delay the implementation of the action or the EU's financial interests:

- Change of the Principal Investigator (PI) or Legal Entity Appointed Representative (LEAR).
- Changes in its legal, financial, technical, organisational or ownership situation or those of its linked third parties.
- Changes in the name, address, legal form, organisation type of its linked third parties.
- Any circumstance affecting the decision to award the grant or compliance with the requirements under the agreement.

In addition, throughout the project lifetime, each beneficiary must keep information stored in the Participant Portal Beneficiary Register up to date, in particular, its name, address, legal representatives, legal form and organisation type.

3.3 Project reporting calendar

The list of official commitments is summarised in Table 1.

Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary	Dissemination Level	Due Date
WP1	D1.1	Kick-off report, agreed and consolidated 1st year work plan	i2CAT	SEN	31 Mar 2023
WP3	D3.1	Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery (I)	AFE	PU	30 Apr 2023
WP2	D2.1	Inter-ecosystem hands-on visits plan	HAM	PU	31 Mar 2023
WP5	D5.1	Communication, dissemination and stakeholders' engagement plan	SHINE	PU	30 Apr 2023
WP1	D1.2	Quality Assurance Plan, and guidelines for consortium operation	i2CAT	PU	31 May 2023
	H1	First draft of virtual space (project management and regional spaces developed) (theglobal.network)	i2CAT		31 May 2023
WP2	D2.2	Col.laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan	F6S	PU	30 June 2023
	H2	Advanced version of virtual space (EU INTEGER community and col.laborathon space)	HAM		30 June 2023
WP1	D1.3	Data Management Plan	i2CAT	PU	31 Jul 2023
WP1	D1.4	Intermediary Report on Data Management Plan	i2CAT	PU	31 Jul 2024
WP3	D3.2	Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery (II)	AFE	PU	31 Aug 2023
WP3	D3.3	Report on main features of the 3 regional Innovation Ecosystem Models	URV	PU	31 Oct 2023
	H3	INTEGER Col.laborathon Regional lessons learnt	URV		31 Oct 2023
WP2	D2.3	INTEGER Platform guidelines	i2CAT	SEN	31 Jan 2024
WP2	D2.4	Report on inter-ecosystem projects and best practices exchanged	HAM	PU	31 Jan 2024
WP2	D2.5	Healthy living systems synergies report	AFE	PU	31 Jan 2024
WP4	D4.1	First draft of comprehensive 3H & 4H integration innovation ecosystems model	i2CAT	PU	31 Jan 2024
	H4	Full deployment of INTEGER virtual space	i2CAT		31 Jan 2024

	H5	INTEGER 4H Collaboratory model draft	i2CAT		31 Jan 2024
WP3	D3.4	Three (3) Col.laborathons Final Reports	F6S	PU	29 Feb 2024
		First Periodic report			30 Apr 2024
WP3	D3.5	Business support intermediate services portfolio	URV	PU	31 Jul 2024
WP4	D4.2	EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted	SHINE	PU	31 Aug 2024
WP4	D4.3	INTEGER 4H col.laboratory comprehensive model: academic papers accepted in scientific publications	i2CAT	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP3	D3.6	Regionalised Incubation and Acceleration Report	URV	PU	31 Jan 2025
WP3	D3.7	Business support final services portfolio	URV	PU	31 Jan 2025
WP4	D4.4	Report on coordination actions with key related initiatives	AFE	SEN	31 Jan 2025
WP5	D5.2	Stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives and impact monitoring report	SHINE	PU	31 Jan 2025
WP5	D5.3	Communication, dissemination and stakeholders' implementation report	SHINE	PU	31 Jan 2025
	H6	Enrolment of key stakeholders of EU INTEGER community	SHINE		31 Jan 2025
		Second Periodic report			30 Apr 2025

Table 1- Official commitments (PU - Public, SEN - Sensitive).

3.4 Deliverables Quality Assurance procedure

The following information intends to define the quality criteria for deliverable preparation and revision. The INTEGER team must take into account the following quality criteria against which every single deliverable will be evaluated:

1. The deliverable must address all aspects related to the purpose and scope for which the related activity is carried out. Each deliverable should provide information according to the scope of the specific work and should be focused on the key aspects of the deliverable scope.
2. Each deliverable should have a coherent depth of information with respect to the deliverable scope, purpose and type of activity described. The deliverable must include an executive summary and proper conclusions if necessary. The contribution of each partner involved should be correctly reported.

3. The impact of the deliverable and any progress beyond the state-of-the-art has to be clearly identified, and any expected output (paper, patents, standard...) included. All background information used in the documents should be linked to appropriate references. Foreground information and results should be clearly described and should be technically supported to avoid any misinterpretation or misunderstanding.
4. All the documents must follow the style guidelines to provide a uniform appearance and structure. A clear and correct language must be used, appropriate abbreviations and references have to be included and listed and a logical order followed.

Deliverable template: The latest version of the document can be found in the folder of WP5 from the INTEGER's Google Drive.

Deliverables acceptance process: The implementation of a quality process includes the preparation of the deliverable, its review and approval process before delivery including the appointment of specific reviewers for each deliverable. Deliverables will be elaborated as a joint effort among the partners involved in the related Work Packages (WP).

Their completion will be under the responsibility of the relevant WP Leader (WPL), who will count on contributions from other partners.

The responsibilities in the consortium are the following:

- The WPL is responsible for fostering the discussions well in advance so the editor can propose a Table of Content (TOC) at least 60 days before the deadline.
- The reviewer(s) will be selected from the partners involved (see proposed distribution). Reviewers will make revision of the deliverable and assess if some modifications or conflict resolution would be needed. The reviewer will assure the conformity of the document with the quality criteria.

Please take into account the following time revision instructions for deliverables quality assurance:

- a) 40 days in advance of the deliverable due date, the WP leader should provide the TOC, and bring the topic to be discussed in the regular monthly meeting.
- b) Three weeks before the due date of the deliverable, the document should be ready for the internal review and quality assurance.
- c) The reviewers will send their feedback on the deliverable at least 10 days before the submission.
- d) In 5 days after receiving the feedback, reviewer's comments have to be addressed by the editor and the parties involved in the writing process.

- e) Two days before the due date, the document should be ready for the submission by the Project Coordinator.

Time to delivery	40 days	21 days	10 days	5 days	2 days	0 days
What	Provide TOC	Ready for Internal revision	Send review	Comments addressed	Ready for submission	Submission
Who	WPL	Editor	Reviewers	Editor	Editor	PC

Table 2- Responsibilities of the internal reviews.

In the following Table 2, an internal reviewer and quality assurance partner is identified for each of the deliverables.

Del. #	Title	WP Lead Beneficiary	Internal Reviewer	Due Date
D1.1	Kick-off report, agreed and consolidated 1st year work plan	i2CAT	HAM	31 Mar 2023
D1.2	Quality Assurance Plan, and guidelines for consortium operation	i2CAT	SHINE	30 May 2023
D1.3	Data Management Plan	i2CAT	F6S	31 Jul 2023
D1.4	Intermediary Report on Data Management Plan	i2CAT	URV	31 Jul 2024
D2.1	Inter-ecosystem hands-on visits plan	HAM	AFE	31 Mar 2023
D2.2	Col-laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan	F6S	HAM	30 Jun 2023
D2.3	INTEGER Platform guidelines	i2CAT	SHINE	31 Jan 2024
D2.4	Report on inter-ecosystem projects and best practices exchanged	HAM	I2CAT	31 Jan 2024
D2.5	Healthy living ecosystems synergies report.	AFE	URV	31 Jan 2024
D3.1	Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery (I)	AFE	I2CAT	30 Apr 2023
D3.2	Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery (II)	AFE	AFE	31 Aug 2023
D3.3	Report on main features of the 3 regional Innovation Ecosystem Models	URV	HAM	31 Oct 2023

D3.4	Three (3) Col-laborathons Final Reports	F6S	URV	29 Feb 2024
D3.5	Business support intermediate services portfolio	URV	SHINE	31 Jul 2024
D3.6	Regionalised Incubation and Acceleration Report	URV	F6S	31 Jan 2025
D3.7	Business support final services portfolio	URV	I2CAT	31 Jan 2025
D4.1	First draft of comprehensive 3H & 4H integration innovation ecosystems model	i2CAT	F6S	31 Jan 2024
D4.2	EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted	SHINE	URV	31 Aug 2024
D4.3	INTEGER 4H collaboratory comprehensive model: academic papers accepted in scientific publications	i2CAT	AFE	30 Nov 2024
D4.4	Report on coordination actions with key related initiatives	AFE	HAM	31 Jan 2025
D5.1	Communication, dissemination and stakeholders' engagement plan	SHINE	I2CAT	30 April 2023
D5.2	Stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives and impact monitoring report	SHINE	F6S	31 Jan 2025
D5.3	Communication, dissemination and stakeholders' implementation report	SHINE	I2CAT	31 Jan 2025

Table 3- Deliverables review responsibilities.

3.5 Milestones

Milestones will be marked as achieved by the PC in the Participant Portal. At least two days in advance of the deadline the Lead Beneficiary of the milestone will send the PC a short paragraph explaining the arguments that support having achieved the milestone. After that this paragraph will be updated on the intranet. In case that is necessary, the Lead Beneficiary will provide as support the necessary documents or reports that will be kept by the PC.

3.6 Periodic Reporting

To comply with article 21.2 of the Grant Agreement, the PC will submit a Periodic Report within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. The Periodic Reporting is submitted through the Participant Portal. In the INTEGER project there are two periodic

reports, first one covering the activity and costs of months 1-12, second one covering months 13-24. Along with the Periodic Report a Financial Report will be submitted. Details on this report will be provided in advance.

3. Dissemination

Dissemination of the project outputs to society is one of the objectives included in the Horizon Europe program. Dissemination however must not collide with the IPR of the partners or with results that need to be protected (see Article 16 of the Grant Agreement and the CA for more information).

In this section we describe the mandatory rules for disseminating the results of the project and how to report the project outputs.

The public website is accessible under <https://integercollab.eu/>. It is developed and managed by SHINE as leader of the Dissemination work package and i2CAT, in coordination with the Project Coordinator. The website is continuously updated with news, publications, events, and relevant information regarding the project.

An initial dissemination and communication plan was delivered (D5.1, Month 4) for the first phase of the project. The final Communication and dissemination activities report will be submitted in Month 24 (D5.3).

In order to maintain the confidentiality and quality of our communication and dissemination activities, any external communication involving unpublished project results or describing the activities of a non-authoring partner, such as scientific articles or formal publications (e.g., white papers), must receive approval from all relevant partners before publication. This measure aims to prevent the premature release of preliminary results and guarantee the overall quality of our communication efforts.

4.1 Acknowledgements

All the publications, conference proceedings, presentations on workshops, seminars, press releases, equipment, communications, patents, standard or public events must take into account the following obligation towards the EC:

■ Publications, conferences and events

Unless the EC requests or agrees otherwise or either it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem as defined in article 17.2

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(b) display the following disclaimer when applicable

“Integer (GA 101096563) has been Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

(c) include the following text:

“INTEGER has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096563.”

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

4.2 Reporting the outputs

All the outputs of the project (papers, proceedings, press releases, non-scientific publications...) and the dissemination actions (assistance to workshops, public demos, fairs...) have to be reported on a monthly basis to ensure a proper dissemination.

Despite this periodic reporting, any relevant output, major result, equipment publicly displayed, patent or standard must be immediately informed.

The outputs of the project will be reported through an event tracking mechanism based on the intranet. This event tracking mechanism will include the following sections:

1. Foreseen of assistance to events: In this section each partner will report the assistance to any event (congress, fair, workshop, demo...) and the objectives of the action.
2. Foreseen organisation of events: In this section each partner will report the organisation of any event related with the dissemination of the project and the foreseen objectives of the event.
3. Event reporting: In this section each partner will report the assistance to events. This report will include the date, place and name of the event, the members of the consortium that assisted, the audience profile and number of assistants, a short report of the results, any presentations or papers.
4. Publications reporting: The publications (book chapters, papers, proceedings, white paper or non-scientific and non-peer reviewed outputs) related with the project will be reported in this section. Each paper has to include the status (submitted, under review or accepted) and include the DOI. Other kinds of publications have to include a link to the content.

As stated in CA the authors must inform the consortium of any foreseen publication at least 20 days in advance. Any objection must be done in writing within 10 calendar days after the receipt of the notice. If there is no objection the publication is permitted.

5. Risk Management

a. Main approach

The risk management process has the following main steps:

Risk Identification: data sources such as information from past projects and subject matter experts' opinions were used to make a first estimation of all potential risks that can impact INTEGER.

Risk Assessment: prioritisation of the risks based on their likelihood and level of impact.

Risk Mitigation: contingency plan with risk mitigation actions to manage the project risks, including risk owners, the ones responsible for monitoring and controlling risks.

Risk Monitoring: Risks must be monitored throughout the project life cycle to be controlled.

b. Update of critical risks

Table 3 presents an updated version of the risks already included in the proposal reevaluating the level of the risks. All the risks identified are considered to be low, except for the first one that is linked with the political situation in east Europe cannot be evaluated.

#	Risk	Mitigation	Updated level of risk
1	Risk of not being able to perform tasks due to unpredictable circumstances like the endanger of extending the war conflict for some countries (like Poland)	Not possible to deal with that risk at the current stage for some partners, so then if it happens the consortium via the project coordinator will discuss with the project officer for designing an ad hoc contingency plan for the remaining tasks.	unknown
2	Due to the COVID-19 crisis, difficulties to perform tasks or organise face-to-face meetings because of restrictions resulting from national emergency measures including travel restrictions, social distancing and confinement	Already having experience on how to deal with such situations, a detailed plan that other partners will continue the work under given resources Face-to-face meetings planned will be adapted to the COVID-19 situation by either transforming them into virtual conferences, webinars or workshops.	low

3	Due to the COVID-19 crisis, low participation of stakeholders within the 3 pilot regions	Stakeholders not mainly dealing with COVID-19 will be selected. The size of meetings will be small enough to fulfil the requirements of social distancing. Virtual and/or blended meetings will be organised.	low
4	Divergence among partners on project direction	Both the Project Coordinator (PC) and the Project Manager (PM) have the essential managerial skills and extensive experience required to enhance communication among partners and effectively find appropriate solutions, ensuring conflicts are resolved friendly..	low
5	Different maturity level of social innovation in the pilot regions	The maturity level of social innovation has been analysed in each of the pilot regions. INTEGER aims to settle the existing bases between social innovators and entrepreneurs and their regional innovation ecosystem.	medium
6	Not possible to establish collaborative and supporting ecosystems at local levels due to other urgent needs	Due to experience of partners knowing how to work, develop the tailored method of collaboration will be in detailed prepared, introduced, and monitored over the project	medium
7	Poor involvement of stakeholders	Continuing engagement and dissemination activities will accompany INTEGER, ensuring active and close participation.	low
8	A partner leaves the project	The consortium will try to assume the partner objectives, responsibilities and resources. In case the responsibilities reallocation is not possible, the consortium will look for possible partners with a similar profile.	low
9	Unexpected delay in project development	The project management is structured to maintain a continuous monitoring on all technical aspects.	low

10	The quality of the disseminated material does not meet the expected standard	Effective measures will be put in place to easily mitigate this risk. The Dissemination Manager will closely monitor and pinpoint underperforming WPs and partners and provide advice and guidance in this respect.	low
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Table 4- Updated list of risks.

The consortium takes a proactive approach to risk management, closely monitoring and making continuous adjustments to ensure the project stays on track. This diligent and proactive approach ensures that the consortium is prepared to navigate challenges and maintain the project's progress, even in the face of unexpected circumstances.

6. Conclusions

Building trust is a fundamental asset of the project, as it sets a solid foundation for collaboration and cooperation among the consortium partners and the various stakeholders involved at every stage of the project. Trust establishes a sense of reliability, transparency and mutual understanding, creating an environment where ideas can be freely shared, concerns can be openly addressed and decisions can be made collectively. This can be transparently traced in the *theglocal.network* platform. By fostering trust, the consortium partners can establish strong working relationships, promoting effective communication and enhancing overall project outcomes.

Moreover, building trust with the different stakeholders engaged in the project is essential for its success. Stakeholders from the quadruple helix, such as social innovators, investors, customers, regulatory bodies and local communities, play a vital role in the project's implementation and impact. Trusting relationships with stakeholders create an atmosphere of shared goals and shared responsibilities, allowing for effective collaboration and collective problem-solving. When stakeholders trust the consortium and its partners, they are more likely to actively participate, contribute their expertise and provide the necessary support to drive the project forward. This not only enhances the project's credibility but also ensures that it aligns with the stakeholders' needs and interests, ultimately leading to a more successful and impactful outcome.

Contingency planning is a fundamental aspect of INTEGER's strategy, which involves not only identifying potential risks but also actively seeking out new risks that may arise during the project development. Furthermore, the consortium regularly reevaluates existing risks to determine if any conditions have changed, which could affect the likelihood or impact of those risks. If any risks are reclassified or their conditions are met, the consortium promptly adjusts their contingency plan to address the evolving circumstances.

Annex-1- Deliverable template

DELIVERABLE TITLE

Call and Topic: HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02

Version 0.0 | xx.xx.xxxx

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number:	
Deliverable title:	
Deliverable version:	
Deliverable Security Class:	
Editor(s):	
Contributor(s):	
Reviewer(s):	
Due Date:	
Delivery date:	
Project name:	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Author(s)/Partner	Main changes

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES

LIST OF TABLES

SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit [1]. Maecenas id risus finibus, pretium mauris eget, vestibulum nisi. Proin mattis condimentum nisl interdum congue. Integer maximus dui eget arcu suscipit, a dictum nunc venenatis. Integer ultrices dolor in imperdiet semper. Morbi et iaculis ligula.

Figure 1. This is the caption of figure 1.

Table 1. This is the caption of table 1.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

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1.3 Methods

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1.4 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

Ut ullamcorper ex quis tortor imperdiet vehicula. Duis lobortis odio nec tortor vestibulum, vel vestibulum enim interdum. Morbi sollicitudin, justo nec rutrum consectetur, elit ligula vulputate risus, et ornare enim turpis et purus. Nam non fringilla mi, et viverra ipsum.

2 HEADING LEVEL 1

2.1 Heading Level 2

2.1.1 Heading level 3

3 CONCLUSIONS.

4 REFERENCES.

Annex-2-Minutes template.

<Project Management Meeting / Monthly Meeting / Other name>	
DATE	<DD Month YYYY> - <HH.mm am/pm CET>
LINK	Meeting link
PROJECT	INTEGER Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions

OBJECTIVES OF THE MEETING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective
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AGENDA

ATTENDEES

- XX

OPEN ACTION POINTS

(Includes list of action points of previous meetings and this meeting)

DATE	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION

MEETING REPORT/MINUTES

1. WPX | Title of the work-package

- Agenda point 1 (Responsible partner)

Summary of the discussion.

ACTION POINTS:

2. WPX | Title of the work-package

- Agenda point 2 (Responsible partner)

Summary of the discussion.

ACTION POINTS:

APPROVED ON/BY: XX

<End of the document>